

Research internship report

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How do edge states get ordered and die:
the effects of anti-ferromagnetic ordering
in a two dimensional topological insulator

Nathan RONCERAY

3rd year student of Ecole Polytechnique

Supervisor: Dr. Adriano AMARICCI

Condensed Matter Theory group

Scuola Internazionale Superiore di Studi Avanzati, Trieste

Introduction

This study was performed during a research internship at the International School for Advanced Studies (SISSA, Trieste), as a 3rd year student of Ecole Polytechnique. During this stay I was a guest of the Condensed Matter Theory group at SISSA, under the supervision of Dr. Adriano AMARICCI.

The research activity of the internship concerned the study of the magnetic ordering effects in a paradigmatic topological insulator in two dimensions. Topological matter is a thriving field, especially because it could yield the missing building blocks for quantum information scale-up. Topological insulators are a special kind of insulators which are distinct from the usual band insulators [1] due to topological properties of the Bloch electrons. Such a non-trivial topology gives rise to many interesting and, in some sense, unusual properties. These systems are insulators, so they have a gap in their band structure, yet they admit metallic (gapless) modes localized at the edge of the material: the *edge states*. The existence of such modes is associated to the precise quantization of the conductivity in these materials. Moreover, when time-reversal symmetry holds, the gapless states are also protected from scattering, making them extremely robust with respect to non-magnetic disorder and weak electronic interactions.

In the presence of strong Coulomb repulsion, electron systems can undergo antiferromagnetic (AFM) ordering. The corresponding symmetry breaking opens a gap in the band structure of the material. We investigate the interplay of an emergent AFM ordering, driven by strong electronic interaction, and topological properties by means of mean-field theory for an interacting version of the Bernevig-Hughes-Zhang (BHZ) model. The onset of magnetic ordering, by breaking time-reversal symmetry, is often expected to obliterate the existence of topological states. When this expectation is not met, exotic states of matter can appear, such as spin Chern insulators [2, 3], axionic insulators [4, 5], etc. We examine the effects of this competition both in bulk geometry and in a finite stripe geometry endowed with gapless edge states. We characterize the phase diagram of the model in both geometrical configurations. In particular we show that close to the transition, the AFM ordering penetrates the stripe from the boundary with a characteristic spatially modulated pattern of the magnetization. We compare the results for the BHZ model to similar but topologically trivial models. We conclude that the presence of the gapless edge states in the topological state prevents the AFM ordering from completely penetrating into the bulk, allowing for the coexistence of magnetic order and non-trivial topology.

Introduction (Français)

Les isolants topologiques sont un type particulier d'isolants qui diffèrent des isolants usuels du fait de propriétés topologiques de leurs fonctions de Bloch. Cette topologie non-triviale leur confère des propriétés intéressantes et inhabituelles. En effet, ces matériaux sont des isolants, possédant un gap dans leur structure de bande, mais ils possèdent également des modes métalliques localisés en surface : les *états de bord*. La présence de tels modes est associée à la quantification précise de la conductivité de ces matériaux. De plus, en présence de symétrie de renversement temporel, il n'y a pas de diffusion et les états de bord sont donc parfaitement conducteurs, ce qui les rend très robustes face au désordre non-magnétique et aux interactions électroniques faibles. Soumis à une forte répulsion coulombienne, les systèmes électroniques peuvent s'arranger selon un ordre antiferromagnétique (AFM). La brisure de symétrie correspondante ouvre un gap dans la structure de bande du matériau. Par une approche de champ moyen, sont étudiées dans ce projet les relations entre l'ordre AFM et les propriétés topologiques du modèle de Bernevig-Hughes-Zhang (BHZ) avec interactions. L'émergence de l'ordre AFM, en brisant la symétrie de renversement temporel, pourrait détruire l'ordre topologique. Cela n'est pas toujours le cas : on trouve ainsi des états exotiques comme les isolants de spin de Chern, les isolants axioniques, etc. L'étude de cette compétition entre ordre magnétique et ordre topologique est effectuée en géométrie infinie et également dans la géométrie d'une bande finie dans une dimension permettant la mise en évidence des états de bord. Le diagramme de phase du modèle est établi dans les deux configurations. On montre en particulier qu'un profil caractéristique oscillant de la magnétisation apparaît près de la transition AFM, pénétrant par le bord dans la bande. Les résultats obtenus sont comparés à des modèles similaires mais topologiquement triviaux. La présence d'états de bords semble empêcher l'ordre AFM de pénétrer complètement la bande et permet la coexistence d'ordre magnétique et d'une topologie non-triviale.

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1 Modeling electrons on a lattice

In this section, we briefly introduce the theoretical framework of this study, i.e. models for interacting electrons on a lattice, as well as an overview of the solving method used in this work.

1.1 The tight-binding approach

In this approach, electrons are considered to occupy the atomic orbitals in a crystal lattice, being tightly bound to the atoms. The electronic wave function can still have a small overlap among neighbouring sites of the crystal, corresponding to a finite tunneling amplitude. In its simplest form a tight-binding system can be defined by considering a lattice whose sites can host either zero, one or two electrons. According to Pauli exclusion principle, two electrons on the same site have to be of opposite spins. Finally, the electrons on the lattice are given a rule to move: the possibility of “hoppings” is introduced according to the overlap of the wave function. The hopping amplitude t_{ij} , computed as the interatomic integral of the atomic potential among neighbouring sites, corresponds to the transfer of an electron from site j to site i . In the second quantization formalism, the resulting contribution to the tight-binding Hamiltonian is $t_{ij}c_{i\sigma}^\dagger c_{j\sigma}$, where the annihilation operators $c_{j\sigma}$ destroys an electron with spin σ at site j while the creation operator $c_{i\sigma}^\dagger$ creates an electron with spin σ at site i .

As a simple example we shall consider here a tight-binding model on a 2D square lattice with nearest neighbour hopping only ($t_{ij} = t\delta_{\langle ij \rangle}$).

$$\mathbf{H}_{kin} = -t \sum_{\langle ij \rangle \sigma} c_{i\sigma}^\dagger c_{j\sigma}$$

Many refinements can be added, such as more complicated lattice structures, several bands (several orbitals per site), and longer-ranged hoppings. We refer to this tight-binding Hamiltonian as the kinetic Hamiltonian. However, it must be observed that this term also includes the periodic potential created by the nuclei. The shape of tight-binding Hamiltonians becomes particularly simple in the Fourier space, using the following transforms:

$$c_{\mathbf{k}\sigma} = \frac{2\pi}{L} \sum_j c_{j\sigma} e^{-i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}_j} \quad ; \quad c_{i\sigma} = \frac{2\pi}{L} \sum_{\mathbf{k}} c_{\mathbf{k}\sigma} e^{+i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}_i}$$

In the basis of the reciprocal space constituted by the annihilation operators $\{c_{\mathbf{k}\sigma}\}$, the Hamiltonian then takes the diagonal form:

$$\mathbf{H}_{kin} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \varepsilon_0(\mathbf{k}) c_{\mathbf{k}\sigma}^\dagger c_{\mathbf{k}\sigma} \quad \text{with} \quad \varepsilon_0(\mathbf{k}) = -2t(\cos(k_x) + \cos(k_y))$$

With more complicated hoppings and geometries, the dispersion $\varepsilon(\mathbf{k})$ changes but the tight-binding Hamiltonian remains (block) diagonal in the reciprocal space. By neglecting electron interactions, the electronic problem is then exactly solvable. More generally this method allows to solve more complicated systems featuring different spin, orbital and lattice degrees of freedom. The corresponding Hamiltonian takes the form:

$$\mathbf{H}_{kin} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \Psi_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{k}) \Psi_{\mathbf{k}}$$

where $\Psi_{\mathbf{k}}$ is a *spinor* collecting the annihilation operators for electrons with momentum \mathbf{k} and different spin, orbital, etc. The band structure is obtained by diagonalizing $\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{k})$ and it is often visualized by plotting the bands along a high-symmetry path in the Brillouin zone.

In the following discussions, we introduce different models by specifying the spinor basis $\Psi_{\mathbf{k}}$ and the corresponding Hamiltonian.

1.2 Interacting electrons : the Hubbard model

Being charged particles, electrons are subject to interactions. Due to Coulomb forces, electrons are attracted by nuclei and repelled by other electrons. While the potential created by the lattice nuclei is handled by the tight-binding approach, the interaction between electrons is not. For a generic material, the effect of the electron-electron interaction can usually be neglected, based on the so-called “one-particle” approximation, which finds its justification in the Fermi liquid theory. However, for a large class of materials called strongly correlated systems, the interaction cannot be neglected with respect to the kinetic part and thus has to be treated explicitly. These systems give rise to complicated many-body problems presenting rich and unconventional physics.

The so-called many-body problem, involving $N \gg 1$ electrons, is in general impossible to solve analytically. Under certain assumptions, very efficient methods have been developed to tackle the problem, and this is the core of the expertise of the Condensed Matter Theory department at SISSA. The topical way to proceed is to take into account the interactions in the second quantization formalism, by keeping the tight-binding Hamiltonian and adding an interaction term:

$$\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{H}_{kin} + \mathbf{H}_{int}.$$

The paradigm of the strongly interacting system, i.e. the simplest and most iconic model of interacting electrons, is the Hubbard Hamiltonian:

$$\mathbf{H}_{int} = U \sum_i \hat{n}_{i\uparrow} \hat{n}_{i\downarrow}$$

Where the operator $\hat{n}_{i\sigma} = c_{i\sigma}^\dagger c_{i\sigma}$ is the population of spin σ electron at position i . Electrons being fermions, the occupation operator has eigenvalues 0 and 1. As such the interaction term expresses the energy cost U of occupying with two opposite spins electrons the same site i . This is the simplest way to model the repulsion between electrons, but it can be refined. In section 3.1, we present an extended version of the Hubbard repulsion accounting for Hund’s coupling when several orbitals are involved. As simple as the basic Hubbard model may seem, it is impossible to solve analytically when the space dimension exceeds 1. Yet, this minimal model can capture the competition between the interaction term and the kinetic energy gain from electron delocalization, which is an essential ingredient in the physics of strongly correlated systems.

1.3 Mean-field theory

The simplest way to treat such complicated interactions is the mean-field theory. When dealing with electrons, this is also commonly called Hartree-Fock’s method. Practically, it neglects the interaction between *fluctuations*. Given two observables \hat{A} and \hat{B} , the mean-field approximation reads: [6]

$$\hat{A}\hat{B} = \langle \hat{B} \rangle \hat{A} + \langle \hat{A} \rangle \hat{B} - \langle \hat{A} \rangle \langle \hat{B} \rangle$$

Neglecting the fluctuation cross term:

$$(\hat{A} - \langle \hat{A} \rangle)(\hat{B} - \langle \hat{B} \rangle) = 0$$

This procedure is called the mean-field *decoupling* of the product $\hat{A}\hat{B}$. In this study, we apply this approximation to decouple the electron population observables $\hat{n}_{i\sigma}$ in the Hubbard interaction term.

$$\mathbf{H}_{int}^{MF} = U \sum_i \left(\langle \hat{n}_{i\uparrow} \rangle \hat{n}_{i\downarrow} + \langle \hat{n}_{i\downarrow} \rangle \hat{n}_{i\uparrow} - \langle \hat{n}_{i\uparrow} \rangle \langle \hat{n}_{i\downarrow} \rangle \right)$$

The mean-field Hamiltonian thus obtained is said to be *quadratic* in the second quantization operators $c_{i\sigma}$, and is therefore diagonal in the corresponding basis. The mean-field approximation guarantees that the Hamiltonian can be diagonalized, which is essential for what follows. Spatial invariance is also assumed, namely the average populations do not depend on the location index i . The many-sites problem becomes a one-site problem.

Within mean-field approximation we can thus diagonalize a complicated Hamiltonian and identify its (approximated) ground state, either by energy minimization or by self-consistency. Given

the spectrum $\{\epsilon_j\}$ of the Hamiltonian, the density of states $D(\epsilon)$ can be obtained, yielding the chemical potential μ and the energy of the system as follows:

$$D(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_j \delta(\epsilon - \epsilon_j) \quad ; \quad \rho = \int_{-\infty}^{\mu} D(\epsilon) f(\epsilon) d\epsilon \quad ; \quad U = \int_{-\infty}^{\mu} \epsilon D(\epsilon) f(\epsilon) d\epsilon$$

The average electron density ρ is assumed to be known here, as we impose the system to be at half-filling. The Fermi distribution $f(\epsilon)$ is set by the temperature. The density of states depends on the spectrum, which depends itself on the electron populations via the interaction part of the Hamiltonian. If we collect the *average*¹ populations in a vector $\mathbf{n} = (n_{\uparrow}, n_{\downarrow})^T$, all the relevant quantities can be seen as functions of \mathbf{n} . The ground state of the system minimizes the free energy $F(\mathbf{n}) = U - TS$, where the entropy S of a collection of non-interacting fermions which can be computed by solving the Hamiltonian. Theoretically (but not necessarily computationally), the most straightforward approach is to directly minimize this function.

An equivalent approach is to find a fixed point of the following iterative procedure [7]:

1. initialize \mathbf{n} with a guess
2. compute the corresponding Hamiltonian $\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{n}) = \mathbf{H}_{kin} + \mathbf{H}_{int}^{MF}(\mathbf{n})$
3. diagonalize $\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{n})$ to get the eigenvectors $\mathbf{A}_{j\mathbf{k}}$ and the eigenvalues $\epsilon_{j\mathbf{k}}$
4. update the population vector \mathbf{n} as follows: $n_{\gamma} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \|\mathbf{A}_{j\mathbf{k}}^{\gamma}\|^2 f(\epsilon_{j\mathbf{k}})$
5. go back to step 2 and iterate until \mathbf{n} converges.

The latter procedure was implemented in this study, first on the simplest Hubbard model to reproduce the results of [7], and then on more complicated models (at zero temperature and half-filling for more simplicity). The convergence criterion was chosen to be $\|\Delta\mathbf{n}_{iteration}\|_{\infty} < \theta$, where θ is the convergence threshold (see appendix A.1).

Many other methods can be used to handle electron interactions. They involve heavy calculations, but are able to capture features that are invisible from mean-field theory. In particular, the so-called *Dynamical Mean-Field Theory* (DMFT) takes into account (local) quantum fluctuations [8].

Application: interaction-driven antiferromagnetic ordering

As a way to learn mean-field theory, how to setup and solve numerically an interacting problem as well as a starting point for increasing complexity, the mean-field procedure introduced above was applied to the case of the Hubbard model. When the interaction strength is high enough, electrons can undergo antiferromagnetic (AFM) ordering, also called Néel order. It means that neighbouring sites host electrons of opposite spin. In order to capture this effect, the unit cell of the lattice has to be doubled, introducing two inequivalent sites A and B.

Figure 1: Doubling of the unit cell

This operation does not only increase the size of the unit cell but also changes the underlying Bravais lattice from a square lattice to a triangular lattice. In order to solve the mean-field

¹the average symbols are dropped using the convention $\langle \hat{A} \rangle = A$

self-consistency, using the iterative approach discussed above, we consider a doubled population vector $\mathbf{n} = (n_{\uparrow A}, n_{\uparrow B}, n_{\downarrow A}, n_{\downarrow B})^T$. Our implementation recovered exactly the results presented in the literature by CLAVEAU and al. [7]. In particular, at half-filling, the system undergoes a paramagnetic-antiferromagnetic phase transition for increasing U .

We will see in the following that such a phase transition also occurs in more complicated systems. The goal of this study is to characterize this transition in the presence of non-trivial *topological* states.

2 Topological insulators

Topological matter has aroused exceptional interest over the last decades, rewarded by the Nobel Prize in 2016. The early theoretical studies dating back to the beginning of the '80s have been extended later with the prediction and the subsequent experimental discovery of the quantum spin Hall state, the paradigm of topological insulators in two dimensions. Such systems are bulk insulators but exhibit metallic edge states, leading to peculiar behaviour and promising applications.

2.1 Introduction to topological matter

The most common example used to introduce the concept of topology is to consider the holes of a tridimensional object: a mug can be smoothly deformed into a torus, but a torus cannot be deformed into a sphere without any discontinuity. Just like a torus cannot be continuously deformed into a sphere, some quantum systems (insulators) cannot be continuously deformed into one another. A *topological invariant* can be associated to such objects, which is the equivalent of the number of holes in the Hilbert space of the Bloch wavefunctions.

The topological properties of electronic systems are related to their band gap. The presence or not of an energy gap in the spectrum of the material allows to distinguish between a metal (gapless) and an insulator (or semi-conductor). However, it was pointed out a decade ago [9, 10, 11, 12, 13] that there exist different kinds of gapped insulators, which can only be distinguished by the topology of their Bloch wave functions. These quantum materials have been dubbed topological insulators. At the interface with a trivial insulator, a topological insulator develops metallic edge states. This phenomenon can be understood as follows: to go smoothly from a topological gap to a trivial gap, one has to close the gap, and this is what happens at the edge.

The computation of topological invariants is a well documented field, but we will not provide a wide overview here, as the minimal systems we study here can be understood with a simplified approach. BERRY discovered that some systems acquire a phase when driven adiabatically along a closed loop in a parameter space. This *Berry phase* correspond to the flux of the so-called *Berry curvature* over the loop in parameter space [14]. The integral of this curvature over the Brillouin zone expresses the topological character of the system (Gauss-Bonnet theorem). We do not enter the details of the computation of the Berry curvature here, but we show how to evaluate the Chern number (the simplest topological index) for the instructive case of a two-level Hamiltonian.

Any two-level Hamiltonian can be written in the Pauli matrices basis $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = (\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z)$ as $\hat{\mathbf{h}} = e_0 \hat{\mathbf{1}} + \hat{\mathbf{d}} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}$. The normalized vector field can then be defined as: $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{k})}{\|\hat{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{k})\|}$. Just like the integral of the curvature of a tridimensional object is related to the number of holes, in the case of a two-level quantum system, one can compute the so-called Chern invariant as follows [12]:

$$C = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{1BZ} (\partial_{k_x} \mathbf{v} \times \partial_{k_y} \mathbf{v}) \cdot \mathbf{v}$$

It corresponds to the number of Berry flux monopoles in the 1st Brillouin zone. For time-reversal invariant systems a similar formula holds for the evaluation of the \mathbb{Z}_2 -index $\nu = \frac{C_{\uparrow} - C_{\downarrow}}{2}$, which characterizes this class (TRS) of topological insulators [15, 11, 12, 13, 16, 17, 18]. In order to get a better idea of these abstract notions, we now examine a model of a topological insulator.

2.2 The BHZ model

A paradigmatic model for topological insulators obtained with a minimum of ingredients is the so-called Bernevig-Hughes-Zhang (BHZ) model. The model was first introduced to predict a peculiar behaviour in *HgTe/CdTe* quantum wells, which were then found to provide an example of quantum spin Hall insulator [15, 11]. However, this model can also be considered more generally as a minimal effective framework to study topological insulators. In the spinor basis $\{\Psi_{\mathbf{k}} = (c_{\mathbf{k}1\uparrow}, c_{\mathbf{k}2\uparrow}, c_{\mathbf{k}1\downarrow}, c_{\mathbf{k}2\downarrow})^T\}$, the BHZ Hamiltonian reads:

$$\mathbf{H}_{kin}^{BHZ} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{k}) & O_4 \\ O_4 & \mathbf{h}^*(-\mathbf{k}) \end{pmatrix}$$

with

$$\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{k}) = \begin{pmatrix} M - 2t(\cos(k_x) + \cos(k_y)) & \lambda(\sin(k_x) - i\sin(k_y)) \\ \lambda(\sin(k_x) + i\sin(k_y)) & -M + 2t(\cos(k_x) + \cos(k_y)) \end{pmatrix}$$

The main features of this model are:

- 2 different orbitals per site, split by a *mass parameter* M
- nearest-neighbour hopping with amplitude t for identical orbitals
- nearest-neighbour hopping with amplitude proportional to λ for different orbitals

The details of the microscopical hoppings of the BHZ model are provided in appendix A.3, Fig. 19. From this point we set $2t = 1$ as the energy unit. As it can be seen from the band structure reported below, the system's gap closes for $M = 2$: at this value of M the system undergoes a *topological phase transition* (c). For $M > 2$, the material is a trivial insulator, with a direct gap (d). For $M < 2$, it is a topological insulator with an indirect gap (a,b).

Figure 2: Band structure of the BHZ model for several values of M ($\lambda = 0.3$).

One way to visualize the topological character of the system is to consider the Berry curvature and to compute the \mathbb{Z}_2 -invariant [12, 17, 18]. The Berry flux in the 1st Brillouin zone is plotted below. The formula given above to compute the \mathbb{Z}_2 -invariant yields $\nu = 0$ for $M > 2$ (c,d) and $\nu = 1$ for $M < 2$ (a,b).

Figure 3: Berry curvature in the Brillouin zone for several values of M ($\lambda = 0.3$). For $M < 2$, the system is topologically non-trivial ($\nu = 1$)

The visualization of the Berry curvature is however not very straightforward, so we present here another way to illustrate the topological character of the system. The key point is to observe

that the computation of the \mathbb{Z}_2 -invariant is equivalent to checking whether the normalized vector field $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{k})$ “wraps” (i.e. covers) the unit sphere. For each \mathbf{k} -point of the discretized 1st Brillouin zone is plotted below its image by the normalized vector field $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{k})$ on the unit sphere. We can see that the vector field wraps the unit sphere for $M < 2$ and is confined in a small region within the superior hemisphere for $M < 2$.

Figure 4: Wrapping of the unit sphere by the BHZ vector field for several values of M ($\lambda = 0.3$, Brillouin zone discretized with 100×100 points)

2.3 Edge states : from bulk to stripe geometry

As mentioned in the introduction of this section, topological insulators have gapless edge states, which do not appear in the bulk calculations reported above. Therefore, we are missing one of the main specificities of topological insulators. While the computation of the \mathbb{Z}_2 -invariant can only be performed for a bulk system, the analysis of the gapless edge states requires the system to be finite in at least one direction. This is a “paradox” of the topological insulators: their properties are closely related to the bulk but the most dramatic effects can only be seen in finite geometry.

The main goal of this study is to investigate a simple topological system in presence of strong correlation-driven magnetic ordering. To this end, we consider a BHZ model in two dimensions both in the bulk and in a finite stripe geometry. The bulk geometry means infinite in both dimension, and is obtained by applying periodic boundary conditions in both dimensions. The stripe geometry is obtained with periodic boundary condition in direction x and open boundary condition in the other direction y [19, 3].

Figure 5: Schematic illustration of the stripe geometry (there can be several orbitals per site)

We define the spinor $\Psi_{xy} = (c_{1A\uparrow}^{xy}, c_{2A\uparrow}^{xy}, c_{1A\downarrow}^{xy}, c_{2A\downarrow}^{xy}, c_{1B\uparrow}^{xy}, c_{2B\uparrow}^{xy}, c_{1B\downarrow}^{xy}, c_{2B\downarrow}^{xy})^T$. Because of the periodic boundary condition along x we can Fourier transform it in this direction, so the tight-binding Hamiltonian can be read in the hybrid basis (k_x, y) :

$$\mathbb{H}_{kin} = \sum_{k_x, y=0}^{N_y-2} \left(\Psi_{k_x y}^\dagger \mathbf{A}(k_x) \Psi_{k_x y+1} + h.c. \right) + \sum_{k_x, y=0}^{N_y-1} \left(\Psi_{k_x y}^\dagger \mathbf{M}(k_x) \Psi_{k_x y} \right)$$

We use a set notation for the stripe Hamiltonian to avoid confusion with the bulk Hamiltonian. The different Hamiltonian blocks read:

$$\mathbf{M}(k_x) = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{m}} & \hat{\mathbf{t}}_x + \hat{\mathbf{t}}_x^\dagger e^{2ik_x} \\ \hat{\mathbf{t}}_x^\dagger + \hat{\mathbf{t}}_x e^{-2ik_x} & \hat{\mathbf{m}} \end{pmatrix} ; \quad \mathbf{A}(k_x) = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{0}_4 & \hat{\mathbf{t}}_y e^{ik_x} \\ \hat{\mathbf{t}}_y e^{-ik_x} & \hat{0}_4 \end{pmatrix}$$

with:

$$\hat{\mathbf{m}} = \begin{pmatrix} +M & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -M & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & +M & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -M \end{pmatrix} ; \quad \hat{\mathbf{t}}_x = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\epsilon}{2} & \frac{i\lambda}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{i\lambda}{2} & \frac{\epsilon}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\epsilon}{2} & -\frac{i\lambda}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{i\lambda}{2} & -\frac{\epsilon}{2} \end{pmatrix} ; \quad \hat{\mathbf{t}}_y = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\epsilon}{2} & \frac{\lambda}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\lambda}{2} & \frac{\epsilon}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\epsilon}{2} & \frac{\lambda}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{\lambda}{2} & -\frac{\epsilon}{2} \end{pmatrix}$$

Introducing the collective spinor $\Psi_{k_x} = (\Psi_{k_x,y})_{y=0\dots N_y-1}$ the kinetic Hamiltonian can be written in a condensed way as:

$$\mathbb{H}_{kin} = \sum_{k_x} \Psi_{k_x}^\dagger \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{M}(k_x) & \mathbf{A}(k_x) & 0 \dots & 0 \\ \mathbf{A}(k_x)^\dagger & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \mathbf{A}(k_x) \\ 0 & 0 & \mathbf{A}(k_x)^\dagger & \mathbf{M}(k_x) \end{pmatrix} \Psi_{k_x}$$

As complicated as the initial Hamiltonian may seem, we end up with a 1D (block tridiagonal) problem. The complexity of the problem is hidden in the size of the spinors, of dimensions: $N_y \times N_{spin} \times N_{orbital} \times N_{site} = 8 \times N_y$ large. In this study, we chose a typical value $N_y = 40$, which means the Hamiltonian we have to solve is 320×320 . Slightly larger and smaller values of N_y have been investigated without finding qualitative difference in the results, as long as the stripe is “large enough” to have a bulk ($N_y \geq 30$). The chosen value is a balance between this condition and computational cost. By diagonalizing this Hamiltonian and plotting it in the 1D refolded (due to the doubling of the unit cell) Brillouin zone, we get the band structure of the stripe (Fig. 6).

In the following we set $\lambda = 0.3$ and, unless mentioned otherwise, $M = 0.5$.

The edge states can be observed in Fig. 6. By using a color that depends on the components of the eigenvectors (red stands for the edge and blue for the bulk), we show here that the metallic states are localized at the edge. As antiferromagnetic ordering (introduced in 1.3) opens a gap Δ_{AFM} of the order of the electron-electron interaction strength U , we can expect the AFM gap to compete with the topological gap of the BHZ model. The onset of AFM ordering, by breaking time-reversal symmetry, is expected to obliterate the topological character as well as the presence gapless edge states. In the following section we study how the emergence of interaction-driven AFM ordering can lead to a suppression of the edge states in a finite system.

Figure 6: Band structure of the BHZ stripe ($M = 0.5$). The Brillouin zone is reduced by half by the doubling of the unit cell

3 Antiferromagnetic transition and topological order

In order to assess the role of topology in the AFM transition, we examined different models: a topological insulator (the BHZ model), as well as variations of it describing either a trivial insulator or a metal. We characterized all three models first in bulk geometry and then in the stripe geometry described above. To begin with we introduce below the electron-electron interactions considered in this study, as we are now dealing with more complicated models than the Hubbard model discussed above.

3.1 Adding electron interactions to topology

We introduced in section 1.2 the single-orbital Hubbard model on the square lattice. The BHZ model involves 2 orbitals per site. In this case we consider a more sophisticated interaction term which takes into account not just the spin, but also the orbital degrees of freedom. One conventional multi-band interaction term is the so-called Kanamori interaction term. This interaction includes a description of the repulsion between pairs of electrons with opposite spin and same orbital (U), opposite spin and opposite orbital ($U' = U - 2J$), or opposite orbital and same spin ($U' - J$). In addition it includes the effects of the Hund's magnetic exchange J , which accounts for the tendency of electrons to maximize their total spin. In its full form the Kanamori interaction reads:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H}_{int} = & U \sum_{i,\alpha} \hat{n}_{i\alpha\uparrow} \hat{n}_{i\alpha\downarrow} + U' \sum_{i,\alpha \neq \beta} \hat{n}_{i\alpha\uparrow} \hat{n}_{i\beta\downarrow} + (U' - J) \sum_{i,\alpha < \beta, \sigma} \hat{n}_{i\alpha\sigma} \hat{n}_{i\beta\sigma} \\ & - J \sum_{i,\alpha \neq \beta} c_{i\alpha\uparrow}^\dagger c_{i\alpha\downarrow} c_{i\beta\downarrow}^\dagger c_{i\beta\uparrow} + J \sum_{i,\alpha \neq \beta} c_{i\alpha\uparrow}^\dagger c_{i\alpha\downarrow}^\dagger c_{i\beta\downarrow} c_{i\beta\uparrow} \end{aligned}$$

In order to preserve full rotational invariance for the spin, orbital and charge degrees of freedom, the two last terms have to be included, namely *spin-flip* and *pair-hopping*. However, in the following discussions we consider only the density-density part of the interaction, neglecting the last two terms. The effects of the spin-flip and pair-hopping terms have been shown to not change qualitatively the results in such systems [20]. Thus the Kanamori interaction Hamiltonian can be simplified to:

$$\mathbf{H}_{int} = U \sum_{i,\alpha} \hat{n}_{i\alpha\uparrow} \hat{n}_{i\alpha\downarrow} + (U - 2J) \sum_{i,\alpha \neq \beta} \hat{n}_{i\alpha\uparrow} \hat{n}_{i\beta\downarrow} + (U - 3J) \sum_{i,\alpha < \beta, \sigma} \hat{n}_{i\alpha\sigma} \hat{n}_{i\beta\sigma}$$

In everything that follows, the value of J was set to $0.25U$, but none of the results are specific to this value. The presence of Hund's coupling favours the formation to high-spin configurations $S = 1$. In particular, if AFM symmetry breaking is allowed, magnetic ordering is observed for strong interactions as in the Hubbard model described in section 1.2.

The interacting bulk BHZ Hamiltonian is obtained by adding the latter interaction Hamiltonian to the bulk kinetic Hamiltonian presented in 2.2. After mean-field decoupling, we determine the ground state of the system for every set of parameters (U, M) using the iterative procedure described above. The result is the following phase diagram, derived considering both the antiferromagnetic order parameter A_z (which will be referred to as the *magnetization* in what follows) and the orbital polarization T_z .²

Figure 7: Bulk phase diagram of the BHZ model

Across the red line, we observe a first-order transition separating the non-magnetic phase from the AFM phase. The first-order line ends in a second-order transition on the $M = 0$ axis. For a given value of M and increasing U , the system goes from a paramagnetic and orbitally polarized

² $A_z = n_{A\uparrow} + n_{B\downarrow} - n_{A\downarrow} - n_{B\uparrow} = n_{A1\uparrow} + n_{B1\downarrow} - n_{A1\downarrow} - n_{B1\uparrow} + n_{A2\uparrow} + n_{B2\downarrow} - n_{A2\downarrow} - n_{B2\uparrow}$
and $T_z = n_1 - n_2 = n_{A1\uparrow} + n_{A1\downarrow} + n_{B1\uparrow} + n_{B1\downarrow} - n_{A2\uparrow} - n_{A2\downarrow} - n_{B2\uparrow} - n_{B2\downarrow}$

state to an antiferromagnetic and orbitally unpolarized state. The dashed line corresponds to the *topological phase transition* determined by the equation: $M_{\text{eff}} = M - \frac{U-5J}{2} = 2$ (see appendix A.2). This is a second order transition which is also associated to a change of the orbital polarization T_z . Interestingly, the evolution of T_z in the quantum spin Hall region between the two transition lines shows a sensitivity to electron interactions: it gradually decreases as it approaches the magnetic transition. On the contrary, such variation is not observed when one considers the magnetization A_z .

As explained before, the most important feature of topological order, i.e. the presence of the edge states, cannot be resolved in the bulk geometry. We present in Fig. 8 the band structure of the correlated BHZ model in the stripe geometry. The edge states disappear for a critical value of the repulsion strength $U_c \approx 1.75$. Within the mean-field approximation our results show that at the first-order transition between the paramagnetic and the antiferromagnetic phase, the edge state suddenly disappear at the critical line. After the line, the band structure of the stripe corresponds to that of a conventional anti-ferromagnetic insulator, with two band sets separated by a symmetry related gap. No notable change from these two configurations is observed below or above the transition upon varying U .

Figure 8: Band structure of the BHZ stripe (a) for low interactions ($U = 1$) and (b) for high interactions ($U = 2$)

3.2 Comparison with non-topological models

To benchmark the effects of the topological states we considered two other topologically trivial models. To validate their use as benchmarks, we first show that their bulk behavior is fairly similar to that of the BHZ model.

First, we consider an insulator with an inter-orbital, non-local, hybridization. This model will be referred to as the *basic insulator* (BI). The corresponding Hamiltonian reads:

$$\mathbf{h}_{BI}(\mathbf{k}) = \begin{pmatrix} M - 2t(\cos(k_x) + \cos(k_y)) & \lambda(\cos(k_x) - i \sin(k_y)) \\ \lambda(\cos(k_x) + i \sin(k_y)) & -M + 2t(\cos(k_x) + \cos(k_y)) \end{pmatrix}$$

The only difference with the BHZ model is the nature of the inter-orbital hybridization, including a cosine of k_x instead of the sine. The microscopical interpretation of these interactions is provided in appendix A.3. The band structure is provided Fig. 9.

Figure 9: Band structure of the basic insulator for several values of M ($\lambda = 0.3$)

Just like the BHZ model, this BI has a direct gap for $M > 2$ and an indirect gap for $M < 2$, the latter being topologically trivial. This can be verified by studying the vector field on the unit sphere as it was done for the BHZ model Fig. 4. The BI vector field never wraps the unit sphere, regardless of the value of M . Furthermore, no particular change in its behaviour is observed at $M = 2$ (Fig. 10). Thus, the corresponding \mathbb{Z}_2 -invariant is always 0 and the system is topologically trivial.

Figure 10: Wrapping of the unit sphere by the BI vector field for several values of M ($\lambda = 0.3$, Brillouin zone discretized with 200×200 points)

Finally, a second model was considered to benchmark the BHZ model behaviour. Using a similar geometry and a similar Hamiltonian shape, but reversing the lower band and using a slightly different inter-orbital hybridization, we obtain a metal. This model is a 2D version of the model introduced by POTERYAEV and al. in [21], the mass parameter M being equivalent to crystal-field splitting.

The corresponding Hamiltonian reads:

$$\mathbf{h}_M(\mathbf{k}) = \begin{pmatrix} 2t(\cos(k_x) + \cos(k_y)) \lambda(\cos(k_x) - \cos(k_y)) \\ \lambda(\cos(k_x) - \cos(k_y)) 2t(\cos(k_x) + \cos(k_y)) \end{pmatrix}$$

We provide the band structure of the metal Fig. 11:

Figure 11: Band structure of the metal for several values of M ($\lambda = 0.3$)

The bulk properties of the two models used as benchmarks are fairly similar to those of the BHZ model. Namely, their bulk $U - M$ phase diagrams are almost identical to that of the BHZ model: antiferromagnetic ordering is observed for high U and low M . The phase diagrams are shown in appendix A.2. The transition values are slightly different and its sharpness changes a bit from one model to another, but the transition *character* remains the same. As similar as the bulk

behaviour of the models may be, we observed major differences in the phenomenology of the AFM transition in the stripe geometry.

3.3 Magnetic behaviour at the edge

The starting point of this study is the result obtained in [3]. Using DMFT, AMARICCI and al. observed that the AFM transition in the correlated BHZ model in a finite stripe geometry occurred through the formation of a spatial modulation of the staggered magnetization. This phenomenon allowed for the coexistence of an AFM phase and a non-trivial topological state.

It is intuitive that something should happen at the edge in the finite geometry: having less neighbours, the edge sites are *effectively more correlated*. Indeed, the relevant quantity for electron correlations is the ratio U/zt , z being the number of neighbours which is smaller at the edge [22, 23, 19]. In this study we checked that these results keep holding with a simpler mean-field approach. Furthermore, we exploited this simpler method to get a more thorough understanding of the observed effect and its relation with the presence of gapless edge states.

First, the mean-field results were found to be consistent with DMFT: the penetration of the AFM ordering into the slab shows remarkable spatial oscillations of the AFM magnetization A_z close to the transition threshold (see Fig. 12a).

Figure 12: Magnetization oscillation in the BHZ stripe. A nonlinear color-scale was used in (b) to emphasize the oscillation

Compared with the bulk behaviour, the transition shows the presence of an intermediate regime, corresponding to a magnetized edge but yet a paramagnetic bulk, for a range of interaction strength $1.59 < U < 1.75$. The system evolves continuously from the paramagnetic (PM) regime towards a regime with a *magnetized edge* (ME). The AFM transition is still of the first-order, but we noticed that the discontinuity at the magnetic transition is smoothed out near the second order critical point at $M = 0$ just as it is in the bulk geometry. In terms of band structure, the edge states which characterize the non-trivial PM phase keep existing in the ME phase. However, in the presence of a finite magnetization, time-reversal symmetry is broken so another symmetry must be present to protect such gapless states. This symmetry is provided by the $U(1)$ group of spin rotation around the easy axis of the magnetization S_z . As such the surviving topological state corresponds to a spin Chern insulating state rather than a quantum spin Hall one. The edge states disappear as the system enters the AFM phase.

We get a clear view of the evolution of the magnetization distribution across the slab with increasing U . Interestingly, the oscillations which characterize the penetration of the AFM ordering are strongly attenuated, typically over a few layers. No penetration over the whole stripe can be observed within reasonable computation time as the system is driven very close to the AFM transition.

In order to understand if the persistence of gapless edge states near the transition acts as a blockage to the penetration of the AFM ordering, we compared these results for the stripe BHZ model with their equivalent in a topologically trivial model, namely the one introduced above as the BI model. The corresponding plots are reported in Fig. 13. Even though the bulk behaviours of the BHZ and BI model are extremely close, these two model show interesting differences when studied

in the stripe geometry. Indeed, the oscillations are much more dramatic for the BI model. Their attenuation is comparatively much smaller: the penetration over most of the stripe is observed before the ME-AFM transition. Besides, the ME phase occupies a much wider range for the BI model ($0.85 < U < 1.75$), as it appears for smaller values of U . Thus, in the presence of gapless edge states, we observe a stronger attenuation of the AFM ordering penetration into the bulk.

Figure 13: Magnetization oscillation in the basic insulator stripe

The metal model showed significantly different results. Indeed, as it can be seen Fig. 14, when increasing U , the core (also called “bulk” even though it should not be confused with the bulk geometry model) of the stripe smoothly magnetizes *before* the AFM transition. A_z^{bulk} refers to the magnetization of the inner layers ($y = N_y/2$). The plot of this quantity shows that the transition is *almost* 2^{nd} order for the metal stripe. This smoothing of the 1^{st} order character can be explained both by the relative smoothness of the metal-AFM transition and a finite-size effect. An oscillation remains, but with respect to this core magnetization. It is plotted on the lower part of Fig. 14.

Figure 14: Magnetization of the metal stripe

On Fig. 15, the order of the transition can be visualized rather well. In accordance with intuition, the closer a layer is to the edge, the more sensitive to electron interaction it is. A much less intuitive result is the spatial oscillation itself: some layers magnetize in an opposite way from others. It clearly appears that the ME phase does not show in the metal stripe as it does in both insulator models.

Figure 15: Layer-resolved magnetization dependence on the interaction strength: $A_z^y(U)$. Here “bulk” refers to the core of the stripe.

In order to quantify the penetration of the oscillation over the thickness of the stripe, we fitted the magnetization profiles with an exponential decay model $A_z(y) = A_0 \cos(\kappa y) e^{-y/\ell}$. The spectral analysis of the profile shows that the signal is spread among many wave vectors, near the transition the spectral distribution is peaked enough to justify such a fitting model.

The results for $\ell_{BHZ}(U)$ and $\ell_{BI}(U)$ are reported Fig. 16. The fit is excellent in the region close to the transition: this is where the oscillation is quantitatively important and it has a close-to exponential decay. The penetration length it yields is indeed bigger for the trivial insulator than for the topological insulator. Unfortunately this simple procedure could not apply to the metal, as the magnetization signal can not be fitted by a similar model. Indeed, as the *core* of the metal stripe directly magnetizes when U is increased, it means a finite penetration length is complicated to define properly. Anyway, such a penetration length has to be much bigger for the metal than for the other two models.

All these results support the claim that topology prevents the oscillation from penetrating into the bulk. The penetration length for both insulator models shows a critical behaviour $\ell \sim (U_c - U)^{-\gamma}$ close to the transition. The values of the critical exponent γ obtained for $M = 0.5$, $\lambda = 0.3$ and $N_y = 40$ are $\gamma_{BHZ} = 0.33$ and $\gamma_{BI} = 0.43$.

Figure 16: Penetration length ℓ as a function of U . The error committed in the approximation by an exponential decay corresponds to the lighter areas (standard deviation).

The edge states of the BHZ stripe are observed to hold in the ME phase. Still, finite magnetization induces a breaking of time-reversal symmetry. For this reason, the edge states observed in the ME phase cannot be helical: there is no connection between the behaviour of spin \uparrow and \downarrow in the absence of time-reversal symmetry. Thus, the ME phase corresponds to a *perturbed but unbroken* topological order. The main feature of this peculiar phase is the magnetization spatial oscillation. Such an oscillation can also be observed in a non-topological model, but in that case it is much less confined to the edge.

Conclusion

In this report we studied the onset of anti-ferromagnetic ordering driven by strong local interaction in a paradigmatic model for two-dimensional topological insulators. Using a mean-field approximation, we investigated the ground state properties of the system in the bulk (periodic boundary conditions in all directions), and for a finite stripe geometry with open boundary conditions in one direction. We have shown the existence of a first-order transition to an AFM Néel phase for a critical value of the interaction strength U_c in the bulk. We also characterized the presence of such a transition in similar model systems with different topological character: a conventional band insulator and a metal.

Interestingly, the AFM transition in the stripe occurs through the formation of an inhomogeneous spatial distribution of magnetization, preceding the complete transition to an AFM phase. The existence of such a non-trivial modulation of the magnetic order allows the AFM order to coexist with the topological state: the boundary of the stripe hosts gapless edge state while having a finite staggered magnetization. The survival of such *vestigial* edge states, no more protected by time-reversal symmetry (broken by AFM ordering), is associated to the persistence of a residual $U(1)$ symmetry. We thus identified a mechanism to create interaction-driven spin Chern insulating states.

Furthermore, we studied the penetration of the AFM distribution inside the bulk of the stripe. Our results show that the magnetic order is attenuated within a spatial length of a few layers, and is not observed to penetrate “smoothly” into the stripe. In order to clarify whether this effect has to be associated to the existence of gapless edge states in the topological insulator, we investigated the behavior of a similar but topologically trivial system near the same AFM transition. We show that for this basic insulator the penetration length of the AFM order is of many layers, which means the AFM order penetration is much less attenuated. We conclude that in the presence of gapless edge states in the topological insulator, the bulk is “protected” from magnetic ordering. At the critical point the gapless edge states are suppressed and the whole system undergoes a transition to an almost uniform Néel state.

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A Appendix

A.1 Details on the mean-field solving procedure

This section describes the algorithm employed to compute the ground state of the interacting electron systems examined in this study.

The Hamiltonian of the problem reads $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{H}_{kin} + \mathbf{H}_{int}$. As explained in 1.3, the kinetic Hamiltonian is block-diagonal in the reciprocal space $\mathbf{H}_{kin} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \Psi_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{k}) \Psi_{\mathbf{k}}$, the size of the blocks being determined by the number of degrees of freedom allowed for an electron of momentum \mathbf{k} (spin, orbital, inequivalent sites). This kinetic Hamiltonian can be fully diagonalized by diagonalizing the blocks $\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{k})$, giving the band structure in the absence of interactions. Adding interactions shifts the total Hamiltonian, but leaves the kinetic part unchanged. It can then be stored once and for all for the computations.

Computation of the interaction Hamiltonian

For the basic Hubbard model, the mean-field procedure replaces the Hubbard repulsion terms of the shape $\hat{n}_\uparrow \hat{n}_\downarrow$ by $n_\downarrow \hat{n}_\uparrow + n_\uparrow \hat{n}_\downarrow - n_\uparrow n_\downarrow$. Using the spinor $\Psi = (c_\uparrow, c_\downarrow)^T$, and the *average* population vector $\mathbf{n} = (n_\uparrow, n_\downarrow)^T$, the corresponding term becomes $\Psi^\dagger \cdot \text{diag}(\Xi \cdot \mathbf{n}) \cdot \Psi - \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{n}^T \cdot \Xi \cdot \mathbf{n}$ where the Hubbard MF shift matrix reads $\Xi = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & U \\ U & 0 \end{pmatrix}$. The first term corresponds to a diagonal matrix in the real-space spinor basis: it is the mean-field shift to the Hamiltonian of the system. The second term, the so-called *Hartree shift* is a number, that corresponds to the product of the averages in the MF decoupling. Using the more complicated Kanamori Hamiltonian, one gets:

$$\Xi_K = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & U - 3J & U & U - 2J \\ U - 3J & 0 & U - 2J & U \\ U & U - 2J & 0 & U - 3J \\ U - 2J & U & U - 3J & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{with} \quad \mathbf{n} = \begin{pmatrix} n_{1\uparrow} \\ n_{2\uparrow} \\ n_{1\downarrow} \\ n_{2\downarrow} \end{pmatrix}$$

If the unit cell is doubled using the same Kanamori Hamiltonian, and introducing the inequivalent sites A and B, one gets $\Xi_{2K} = \begin{pmatrix} \Xi_K & 0 \\ 0 & \Xi_K \end{pmatrix}$ with $\mathbf{n} = (n_{1\uparrow A}, n_{2\uparrow A}, n_{1\downarrow A}, n_{2\downarrow A}, n_{1\uparrow B}, n_{2\uparrow B}, n_{1\downarrow B}, n_{2\downarrow B})^T$.

The shift matrix used for the stripe is $\Xi_S = \begin{pmatrix} \Xi_{2K} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \Xi_{2K} \end{pmatrix}$, that matrix being $8N_y \times 8N_y$. No

matter how big the vectors and the matrix may be, the interaction Hamiltonian reads, in the mean-field approximation:

$$\mathbf{H}_{int}^{MF} = \text{diag}(\Xi \cdot \mathbf{n}) - \left(\frac{1}{2} \mathbf{n}^T \cdot \Xi \cdot \mathbf{n} \right) \mathbf{1}$$

Being diagonal in real space, it is also diagonal in reciprocal space. The iterative procedure consists in repeated diagonalizations of the full Hamiltonian $\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{n}) = \mathbf{H}_{kin} + \mathbf{H}_{int}^{MF}(\mathbf{n})$, which lead to updates of the populations until convergence to the approximated ground state is reached.

Convergence of the algorithm

The selected convergence criterion is $\|\Delta \mathbf{n}_{\text{iteration}}\|_\infty < 10^{-5}$ for the stripe and $\|\Delta \mathbf{n}_{\text{iteration}}\|_\infty < 10^{-6}$ for the bulk. It corresponds to a balance between the speed of the algorithm and the requested precision for reliable results.

As it can be expected, convergence is very slow in the region of main interest near the transition. Typically, in this region, 10 to 100 iterations were necessary at each step to obtain convergence. In some cases, convergence could not be observed near the transition within reasonable time. The number of iterations and the convergence criterion had to be optimized to take this into account

and make the non-convergence area as small as desired. Also, due to the trapping of the algorithm in local minima of the energy landscape, convergence was sometimes observed towards non-physical metastable states. Especially, it was observed in the stripe geometry. Metastability was checked by computing the energy, and the way we found to circumvent this problem was to systematically start from AFM configurations and decrease U rather than doing it the other way around.

A.2 Bulk phase diagrams of the trivial insulator and the metal

The bulk phase diagrams for the benchmark models are very similar to the BHZ one, so they were put in this appendix. One should note that here, the dashed line is still present but it does not correspond to a *topological* phase transition anymore. It corresponds to the closing of the gap. For the basic insulator, the gap is indirect below the dashed line. For the metal model, the gap is closed below the dashed line. The slope of the dashed line is given by the relation $M_{\text{eff}} = M - \frac{U-5J}{2}T_z = 2$ which corresponds to the closing of the gap. It can be checked by regrouping the terms yielded by the MF decoupling of the Kanamori interaction Hamiltonian in the spinor basis and then computing the eigenvalues.

Figure 17: Basic insulator

There were convergence issues for the metal model close to the AFM transition. It is rather normal as, unlike the insulators, it has a Van Hove singularity (divergence of the density of states) at the Fermi level. The AFM transition tries to open a gap in the middle of this singularity, which leads to numerical issues. The discretization of the 1st Brillouin zone had to be much finer for this model to account for this specificity. N_k was set to 128 for the stripe and 256 for the bulk, whereas it was set to 32 for the other models in both geometries.

Figure 18: Metal

A.3 Construction of the stripe kinetic Hamiltonian

The reconstruction of the microscopical hoppings from the expression of the orbital interaction is a delicate element of this study. Indeed, most papers only provide the \mathbf{k} -space interaction expression: it is the case for the BHZ model as well as the metal model. Thus, in order to solve the stripe model that uses a *hybrid* basis (k_x, y) , the microscopical hoppings had to be derived from the models. In order to get them, the procedure is to *start from the bulk model*, reverse Fourier transform the Hamiltonian $\sum_{\mathbf{k}} \Psi_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \mathbf{H}_{\mathbf{k}} \Psi_{\mathbf{k}}$. Then we identify the corresponding terms in the shape $\Psi_{\mathbf{R}}^\dagger \mathbf{T}_{\mathbf{r}} \Psi_{\mathbf{R}+\mathbf{r}}$. The matrix elements of $\mathbf{T}_{\mathbf{r}}$ correspond to the microscopical hoppings, which are provided Fig. 19.

Figure 19: Hoppings for the BHZ model

The real space bulk Hamiltonian $\mathbf{H}_{\text{bulk}} = \sum_{\mathbf{R}=(x,y)} \sum_{\mathbf{r}} \Psi_{\mathbf{R}}^\dagger \mathbf{T}_{\mathbf{r}} \Psi_{\mathbf{R}+\mathbf{r}}$ (where the sum over \mathbf{R} is infinite and the sum over \mathbf{r} runs over the identified non-zero hoppings) is then restricted to a finite number of y layers: $\mathbb{H}_{\text{stripe}} = \sum_{x=0}^{\infty} \sum_{y=0}^{N_y-1} \Psi_{(x,y)}^\dagger \mathbf{T}_{\mathbf{r}} \Psi_{(x,y)+\mathbf{r}}$. Fourier transforming again, but *only along the x-axis*, the hybrid Hamiltonian is obtained as introduced directly section 2.3.

We provide below the expression of the hoppings for the BI and metal models.

$$\text{BI:} \quad \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{\mathbf{x}} = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\epsilon}{2} & \frac{\lambda}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\lambda}{2} & \frac{\epsilon}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\epsilon}{2} & \frac{\lambda}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\lambda}{2} & -\frac{\epsilon}{2} \end{pmatrix}; \quad \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{\mathbf{y}} = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\epsilon}{2} & \frac{\lambda}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\lambda}{2} & \frac{\epsilon}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\epsilon}{2} & \frac{\lambda}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{\lambda}{2} & -\frac{\epsilon}{2} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\text{Metal:} \quad \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{\mathbf{x}} = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\epsilon}{2} & \frac{\lambda}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\lambda}{2} & \frac{\epsilon}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\epsilon}{2} & \frac{\lambda}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\lambda}{2} & -\frac{\epsilon}{2} \end{pmatrix}; \quad \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{\mathbf{y}} = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\epsilon}{2} & -\frac{\lambda}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\lambda}{2} & \frac{\epsilon}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\epsilon}{2} & \frac{\lambda}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\lambda}{2} & -\frac{\epsilon}{2} \end{pmatrix}$$